

Editors' Introduction

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ETICA: A Yearbook of Ethics and Public Affairs is the research organ of the American University of Armenia's (AUA) Center for Ethics in Public Affairs (ETICA), established in March 2025. The primary aim of the *Yearbook* is to publish peer-reviewed articles based on research conducted in Armenia and internationally, examining issues of significance to public affairs and their ethical implications. ETICA will also publish invited articles by notable keynote speakers from thematic international conferences organized by the Center. The *Yearbook* is published annually, in both print and online formats and is made available as Diamond Open Access through funding from the Horizon Europe ERA Chair ETICA programme at AUA.

Each *ETICA* volume will be organized around a distinct theme linked to the research carried out at the Center for Ethics in Public Affairs. This first volume of the *Yearbook* is the culmination of a key part of the research conducted in Armenia on the topic of science, expertise, and public policy under the aegis of the Horizon 2020 research project Policy, Expertise, and Trust in Action (PERITIA). The volume is divided into two sections. Section I comprises four invited and peer-reviewed philosophical papers addressing topics in social and political epistemology. They build on and expand the authors' contributions to a conference on the Ethics of Trust, organized by the PERITIA project at AUA. Section II consists of articles developed from working papers presented and discussed during four workshops on science and expertise in Armenia, supported by the AUA Acopian Center for the Environment within the framework of PERITIA Horizon 2020 project. All papers underwent double-blind peer review, both international and Armenian, and were extensively revised in light of referees' comments.

The rationale for choosing the theme of science, policy, and expertise lies in the crisis currently facing democracies worldwide. Democracies indeed are undergoing a challenge of durability. Populists, technocrats, epistocrats, as well as various authoritarian regimes, confront them on multiple fronts. One line of attack targets democracy's knowledge problem: in democracies, ultimate political power belongs to the people, yet they lack the knowledge necessary to rule well. Empirical evidence shows that the general public is poorly informed about political and social realia (Carpini & Keeter, 1989; Bennett, 2003; Somin, 2016). Moreover, there are well-known arguments on why individual citizens have little interest in learning how to vote well (Downs, 1957). As a result, some critics of democracy argue that democracies led by the majority opinion cannot make epistemically robust political decisions. If this were true, and if this were the whole story, one might conclude that democracies are epistemically inferior to

other political regimes. That is, one might conclude that political decisions reached democratically are less justified and less conducive to the public's goals and the common good than those produced under other political regimes. As Kitcher (2020) observed, the problem of democracies is that "they turn their back on the advice of the wise and allow for a tyranny of ignorance" (p. 90). Even if democracies are politically and morally better than other regimes, the argument goes, they are epistemically worse than some other regimes (Brennan, 2016).

The knowledge problems that democracies face have numerous aspects. One is that public knowledge (ignorance) of specific facts can be created by special interest groups for strategic purposes. Knowledge carries a salient political dimension because it affects people's choices and behavior. People's actions are guided by their beliefs, which in turn depend on public education systems, traditional and online media, and other information agents. This is why controlling communication and knowledge transfer is a contested ground for political struggle. The political positioning for engineering public knowledge may concern relatively transient issues, such as managing a politician's public image or framing a particular policy proposal, or it may concern more fundamental and lasting issues, such as the causes of climate change or a reigning pandemic. As knowledge as well as ignorance can serve as political resources, various political agents struggle to produce the public knowledge (or ignorance) most conducive to their goals. This at times leads to polarization and to situations where large segments of society are in separate epistemic bubbles.

If political elites and the public disagree on issues that are profound—if the disagreement is intense and touches on vital interests—the stability of the political community may be put at risk. Thus, in addition to agreements on the mechanisms and procedures of political decision-making, the transfer of power, the distribution of scarce resources, etc., political communities also need to agree on at least some basic empirical, political, and normative truths. Examples of such truths include that science is a highly reliable means of settling empirical disputes, that the majority rule is an acceptable way for settling major political issues, and that legal courts need to be independent from the executive branch.

Another aspect of the knowledge problem that democracies face concerns the role of science-backed experts. It is widely recognized, both within academia and among the general public, that accuracy—and indeed truth—about empirical matters is important to individuals and political communities. Yet, general agreement on empirical facts is not sufficient. Addressing practical issues also requires answering normative questions, whether explicitly or implicitly. Political communities must decide on food standards, methods of preventing or curing diseases, ways of distributing scarce resources, etc. Fulfilling these tasks requires highly specialized em-

pirical knowledge and technical expertise, but it also requires awareness of and engagement with normative questions.

Because of unequal distribution of knowledge, citizens have to rely on expert knowledge to solve almost any personal or public problem they encounter. Hence, there is a need to identify persons who not only possess the requisite expertise but also act with good will and integrity to help solve personal, social, and political issues. In addition to identifying the right people among whom epistemic labor may be divided, societies must also devise a reliable mechanism for aggregating the expertise of a variety of experts who at times, may represent very different disciplines.

Many countries and international organizations have developed guidelines for governments to help them better address the knowledge problem. These guidelines propose ways to democratize and improve the quality of expert advisory processes. The Republic of Armenia seems to lag behind in this regard. With this volume of *ETICA*, we hope to contribute to raising awareness of the issue and to bridging the gap between Armenia's current stance and the best global practices.

This volume comprises eight articles by authors representing different disciplines. The entries range from theoretical explorations to direct engagements with socio-political challenges in contemporary Armenia. Papers in Section I are on theoretical issues of political epistemology.

The first article, by Maria Baghramian and Silvia Caprioglio Panizza, is an extensive literature review of recent philosophical thinking on the question of trust and its ethical implications. It sets the stage for many of the subsequent entries by outlining and critically engaging with some key issues under discussion in this volume, including trust in experts and the phenomenon of distrust. The paper also aims to act as a teaching and research resource for those interested in the topic of trust.

The second entry, "Widespread Puzzling Beliefs" by Paul Boghossian, is a new development in the author's longstanding and well-known defence of the values of rationality and reason. The paper examines the drivers of the current pervasive mistrust of science and expertise in the United States and argues that the most significant contributing factor, alongside the pernicious impact of social media, is the failure of the educational system in teaching the significance of science and critical thinking.

The third article, "Against Epistocracy" by Åsa Wikforss, draws on the findings of the major interdisciplinary Swedish-funded project, "Knowledge Resistance", at the University of Stockholm, led by Wikforss. The paper focuses on the topic of epistocracy, the view that political decisions should be made by experts rather than by the general public. Wikforss urges us not to underestimate the epistemic strengths of representative democracies. Moreover, she argues that political decisions depend not only on factual beliefs but on values and goals which should not be left to unelected experts.

The final entry in Section I, “Voter Competence and Epistemic Arguments for Democracy” by Arshak Balayan, examines the concept of “epistemic democracy” and argues that democracy is superior to other political systems not only morally, but also epistemically. By citing the examples of Condorcet’s Jury Theorem (CJT) and the Diversity Trumps Ability Theorem (DTAT), the paper argues that inclusive democratic deliberation, even when accompanied by free and fair elections, will not fully satisfy democratic needs or outperform expert bodies. To fulfil their epistemic function, democracies need to rely on experts. The author argues that an institutionalized form of expertise could provide a better way to develop democracies.

Section II furthers the discussion of the public role of experts in policy decisions by adding an empirical and practical dimension to the philosophical investigations of the topic in Section I.

“Taking Advice or Sticking to Their Guns?”, the first article in Section II, is co-authored by Laura Prokić, Yevgenya Paturyan, Liana Simonyan, and Gohar Geghamyan. The authors present an empirical study on how the younger generation of Armenians view the impact of expert advice on policy decisions. Using policy scenario exercises, the article concludes that participants often did not consider expert advice when making policy decisions. This tendency was particularly strong when the course of action recommended by the experts in the policy scenarios conflicted their prior beliefs and judgements. The authors conclude that their findings demonstrate the need to strengthen the younger generation’s understanding of the role of expert advice in policy matters.

The sixth article, by Milena Baghdasaryan, published in *Armenian*, discusses some of the shortcomings of environmental impact assessments (EIAs) of mining companies. Utilizing the existing literature, Baghdasaryan illustrates that EIAs often underestimate the future impacts of projects and overestimate the effectiveness of mitigation measures. Shortcomings of EIAs include being politicized rather than being based on genuine scientific knowledge, overlooking some environmental risks, the unaccountability of experts implementing EIAs, and more. Part of the explanation of the shortcomings of EIAs, as seen by Baghdasaryan, is contemporary neoliberalism, which favours deregulation and economic growth rather than sustainability. The paper concludes with a case study of the EIA of the Amulsar mine project in Armenia.

The seventh article, by Anahit Karapetyan, Marine Khachatryan, and Mery Babayan, also published in *Armenian*, examines state and public discourse of science in the post-war (2020) period, comparing trends in discussions of science before and after the 2020 Nagorno-Karabakh war. The paper examines state projects, public discussions, and social initiatives across these two periods to identify key characteristics of the dynamics

of public discourse on science. The authors conclude that: (a) prior to the 2020 Nagorno-Karabakh war, plans for the development of science and for making the country scientifically competitive were developed mostly by bureaucrats and saw little result; (b) following the war, many academics joined the discourse, contributing new perspectives on how to advance Armenia's research and design sector.

The eighth article, the final entry in this volume, is by Arthur Grigoryan, whose contribution fulfills *ETICA*'s aspiration to publish peer-reviewed work not only from academics but also from those working at the coalface of policymaking. Grigoryan's "Expert and Scientific Advice in Public Policymaking in Armenia" addresses the concern that while reliance on expert advice in solving societal problems is commonplace in many developed countries, it is scarce in developing countries such as Armenia. Grigoryan argues that two key tools are needed for effective decision-making: access to high-quality, real-time data and the integration of independent expert advice into the policymaking process. Using evidence-based policymaking in the United States as a benchmark, the paper concludes with some practical recommendations on how to incorporate expert advice into public policymaking in Armenia.

The publication of this inaugural volume has taken longer than we anticipated, and as editors we are grateful to all who have supported the project over the past years. We owe our foremost thanks to the contributors, whose essays made the launch of *ETICA: A Yearbook of Ethics and Public Affairs* possible. We are equally grateful for their admirable patience while the organizational foundations of this publication, as an ongoing series, were laid and the volume was brought to completion. We are indebted to the participants in the four PERITIA workshops on science and expertise held at AUA in 2022 for their helpful comments on the earlier drafts of the papers published here. Their insights and engagement enriched the intellectual background of this volume. Our sincere appreciation also goes to the anonymous peer reviewers, whose careful assessments ensured the scholarly rigor of the contributions published here. Finally, we extend our heartfelt thanks to the Director of AUA Press, Shushan Avagyan, for her steady guidance throughout the publication process and to the production team, Nazeni Hovakimyan and Ovsanna Markarian, for their excellent work on this inaugural volume.

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